

7-mile	-0.7	-1.63
Altamont Prairie	0.21	-0.47
Brookings Prairie	1.71	-0.82
Coteau Lake	-1.82 ●	-2.54 ●
Coteau Prairie	1.46	-0.61
Cox	-1.08 ●	-2.25 ●
Crystal Springs	-1.63 ●	-2.33 ●
Deer Creek	-0.62	-1.06
Gary Gulch E	-0.92	-0.25
Gary Gulch W	-1.12	-0.55
Hole in the Mountain	-1.48 ●	-1.79 ●
Jacobson Fen	0.34	0.7
Lake Ketchum	-1.27 ●	-1.95 ●
McKillican	-0.73	-1.45
Overland	-0.74	-1.09
Punished Woman Grazed	0.04	-1.2
Punished Woman Seeded	-1.43 ●	-2.06 ●
Round/Bullhead	-1.31 ●	-2.24 ●
Severson	0.82	0.14
Sioux Prairie	-1.41 ●	-1.83 ●
Wike	-0.2	0.6
	MPD	MNTD

SES

